

Crystal structure, spectral characterization and biological evaluations of vanillin-N⁴-phenylsemicarbazone

S. R. Layana^a, V. L. Siji^b, M. R. Sudarsanakumar^{*a†}, S. Suma^c, M. R. Prathapachandra Kurup^d and T. S. Sikha^a

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Mahatma Gandhi College, Thiruvananthapuram-695 004, Kerala, India

[†]Department of Chemistry, V. T. M. N. S. S. College, Dhanuvachapuram, Thiruvananthapuram-695 503, Kerala, India

E-mail : sudarsanmr@gmail.com

^bDepartment of Chemistry, All Saints' College, Thiruvananthapuram-695 007, Kerala, India

^cDepartment of Chemistry, Sree Narayana College, Chempazhanchy, Thiruvananthapuram-695 587, Kerala, India

^dDepartment of Applied Chemistry, Cochin University of Science and Technology, Kochi-682 022, Kerala, India

Manuscript received online 02 February 2016, accepted 04 April 2016

Abstract : A novel semicarbazone, vanillin-N⁴-phenylsemicarbazone (NVAN) has been synthesized and characterized with the help of microanalytical, spectroscopic and single crystal X-ray diffraction studies. Amido form of NVAN crystallizes in triclinic space group P $\bar{1}$. The intermolecular hydrogen bonding and the $\pi\cdots\pi$ interactions resulting in a 2D network structure which stabilizes the molecule.

Keywords : Single crystal X-ray diffraction, mass spectrometry, thermogravimetry, antibacterial, DNA cleavage.

Introduction

Semicarbazones are the condensation products of a semicarbazide with an aldehyde or a ketone and having the general formula, R₁R₂C=N-NH(CO)-NH₂. They are emerging as promising ligands in coordination chemistry in light of their excellent metal binding capability. Last few decades showed a plethora of studies in the field of semicarbazones because of their structural properties and broad spectrum of applications in various fields. Their biological applications include antibacterial, antifungal, antihypertensive, hypolipidemic, antineoplastic, hypnotic and anticonvulsant activities¹⁻⁷. Besides, they find applications in analytical chemistry. Semicarbazones can be hydrolysed to the original carbonyl compound and hence they are useful for the isolation, purification and characterization of carbonyl compounds⁸. They are also used as protected carbonyl compounds in organic synthesis⁹⁻¹². Semicarbazones exist in two tautomeric forms; amido and iminol forms (Scheme 1). The structural diversity during

complexation depends upon the coordination number of metal ion used as well as the denticity of the ligand¹³. They can coordinate to the metal ion either as a neutral or as a monoanionic bidentate ligand. The coordinating ability of semicarbazone is further enhanced by substitution at N⁴-position. The N⁴-substituted semicarbazones show sedative hypnotic activity and anticonvulsant activity with less neuro toxicity¹⁴.

Scheme 1. Amido-iminol tautomerism.

Studies have reported that vanillin derivatives show broad range of biological activities. Vanillin hydrazones exhibit antibacterial activity¹⁵⁻¹⁷. Vanillin semicarbazones are potential anticancer agents¹⁸. In light of the above reports we have concentrated on a novel semicarbazone,

vanillin- N^4 -phenylsemicarbazone (NVAN). Here we report the synthesis, crystal structure, spectral, thermal and biological studies of NVAN. The structure of NVAN showing IUPAC numbering is given (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2. Structure of NVAN showing IUPAC numbering.

Materials and methods :

Vanillin (Aldrich) and N^4 -phenylsemicarbazide (Alfa Aesar) used were of AR grade. AR methanol for synthesis (Merck) was used without purification.

Physical measurements :

The carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen content of the compound was determined using Vario EL-III CHNS analyzer. The IR spectrum was recorded on a Thermo Nicolet Avatar 370 DTGS spectrometer using KBr pellets in the range $4000\text{--}400\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The electronic spectrum of the compound was recorded using Varian Cary 5000 spectrometer in the range $200\text{--}800\text{ nm}$. The ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra of the compound in $\text{DMSO-}d_6$ were recorded on Bruker Avance III, 400 MHz spectrometer. Thermogravimetric investigation was carried out in nitrogen atmosphere with a heating rate of $10\text{ }^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ using Perkin-Elmer Diamond TG/DTG analyzer. The mass spectrum of the compound was recorded in HREMI, Thermo Scientific Exactive System. The single crystal X-ray diffraction data of the title compound was collected in a Bruker axis kappa APEX2 CCD Diffractometer with $\text{Mo K}\alpha$ ($\lambda = 0.71073\text{ \AA}$) at 296 K . A crystal with approximate dimensions $0.15 \times 0.20 \times 0.25\text{ mm}^3$ was selected for data collection. Data collection and reduction were performed by APEX2, SAINT/XPREF¹⁹ programs. The structure was solved and refined using SHELXL-97^{20,21}. All non-hydrogen atoms were refined with anisotropic thermal parameters. All hydrogen atoms with the exception of those on nitrogen atoms were geometrically fixed and refined using a riding model. The hydrogen atoms on nitrogen atoms were located from the difference Fourier map and refined isotropically. Molecular graphics employed was Diamond Version 3.1f²².

Biological studies :

Antibacterial study :

In vitro antibacterial activity of the title compound was investigated using agar-well diffusion method. The compound was screened against two Gram-positive and three Gram-negative bacteria. The activity of the compound was found out by measuring the diameter of the zone of inhibition in millimeter. The antibacterial activity was compared with a standard antibiotic Gentamycin. The Muller and Hinton agar and the nutrient broth were prepared and poured in the petriplates and allowed to cool. The petriplates were seeded with the tested organism. After seeding, wells of approximately 10 mm were bored using a well cutter and the investigated compound of desired concentrations was added. The plates were incubated at $37\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 2 h.

DNA cleavage study :

The DNA cleavage study of the compound was conducted by Agarose gel electrophoresis method. The ability of different fractions to protect super coiled pUC18 DNA from harmful effects of hydroxyl radicals generated by Fenton's reagent was assessed by the DNA nicking assay. The DNA cleavage experiment was carried out by digesting $10\text{ }\mu\text{L}$ of plasmid DNA in $10\text{ }\mu\text{L}$ Fenton's reagent ($30\text{ mM H}_2\text{O}_2$, 50 mM ascorbic acid, and 50 mM FeCl_3) followed by the addition of $10\text{ }\mu\text{L}$ of samples. The mixture was then incubated for 30 min at $37\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and the DNA mixture was analyzed on 1.5% agarose gel. The stained gel was visualized using a gel documentation system (E gel imager, Invitrogen).

Synthesis of vanillin- N^4 -phenylsemicarbazide :

NVAN was synthesized by refluxing hot methanolic solutions of vanillin (0.152 g , 1 mmol) and N^4 -phenylsemicarbazide (0.151 g , 1 mmol) in presence of a few drops of dilute acetic acid (Scheme 3). On slow evaporation, colorless block crystals of NVAN separated out. It was then filtered, washed with ether and dried over P_4O_{10} *in vacuo*. The compound was recrystallized from methanol. NVAN is soluble in common organic solvents and Lewis bases such as in DMF and DMSO, but insoluble in water. Yield : 78%, m.p. $184\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$; Found : C, 63.78; H, 5.49; N, 14.86. Calcd. : C, 63.15; H, 5.26; N, 14.73%.

Scheme 3. Synthesis of vanillin-N(4)-phenylsemicarbazone.

Results and discussion

Spectral characterization :

UV-Visible spectrum :

The absorption peak at 271 nm corresponds to π - π^* transition and the peak at 340 nm is attributed to n - π^* transition associated with azomethine linkage²³. There is no band between 400–800 nm. This transparency makes the compound a potential candidate for NLO applications^{24,25}.

FT-IR spectrum :

The peak at 3348 cm^{-1} ^{26,27} is assigned to OH stretching frequency. The medium band observed at 3214 cm^{-1} ²⁸ is assignable to ^4NH stretching vibration. The strong band at 1666 cm^{-1} is assigned to C=O stretching frequency. The ^2NH stretching frequency is observed at 3105 cm^{-1} . This confirms the existence of amido form of the compound in solid state^{29,30}. The IR spectrum shows a me-

dium band at 1598 cm^{-1} ³¹ which is attributed to C=N stretching mode. The band at 1240 cm^{-1} is assigned to C–O stretching vibrations. A weak band at 1190 cm^{-1} is due to C–N stretching mode. The medium band at 1039 cm^{-1} is assigned to N–N stretching vibrations³². The medium bands at 3070 and 3010 cm^{-1} are ascribed to the aromatic C–H stretching modes. The C–H asymmetric and symmetric stretching vibrations in the methoxy group are observed at 2938 and 2832 cm^{-1} respectively.

^1H NMR and ^{13}C NMR spectra :

The ^1H NMR spectrum and the spectral assignments are given in Fig. 1. The sharp singlet at 3.8 ppm corresponds to the methoxy protons and the singlet at 7.9 ppm is attributed to the -OH proton in the vanillin part²⁶ of NVAN. The δ values in the range 6.90–7.67 ppm are assigned to the aromatic protons of the two phenyl rings. The N(2) proton gives a sharp peak at δ 10.53 ppm.

Fig. 1. ^1H NMR spectrum of NVAN.

Downfield shift of this proton is due to nearby hetero atoms (azomethine nitrogen and the carbonyl oxygen) and are decoupled by electrical quadrupole effects. The N(3) proton is also downshifted and is observed at 8.83 ppm because of the presence of the phenyl group and intramolecular hydrogen bonding interactions with N(1)³³. Coupling interactions of N(2) and N(3) protons are absent which confirms the non-availability of protons on neighboring atoms. A signal observed at δ 9.39 ppm is assigned to the C(7) proton. The low field position of this proton is due to the adjacent electronegative nitrogen N(1) and also due to the increased charge density on N(1) resulted by its intramolecular hydrogen bonding interactions with N(3).

The ¹³C NMR spectrum taken in DMSO-*d*₆ along with its assignment is shown in Fig. 2. The proton decoupled ¹³C NMR spectrum give 12 different peaks for twelve unique carbon atoms. As a result of the conjugative effect of the semicarbazone skeleton N(1)–N(2)–C(8)–N(3), the

downshifted signals at 147.9 and 148.3 ppm respectively²⁶.

Mass spectrum :

The mass spectrum and the mode of fragmentation of NVAN is given in Figs. 3 and 4 respectively. The mass spectrum of NVAN shows peaks at 286.11950 [M+H]⁺, 193.06137, 150.05544, 167.08200, 308.10141 and 330.08334. The peaks at 308.10141 and 330.08334 are due to the adduct ions [M+Na]⁺ and [M+2Na-H]⁺ respectively^{35–38}. The base peak is due to the metal adduct ion [M+Na]⁺. From the [M+H]⁺ peak, the molecular weight of the compound can be deduced as 285.1195, which is similar to the calculated value (285.3018).

Crystal structure of NVAN :

The photograph of crystalline NVAN is shown in Fig. 5. The molecular structure of the NVAN along with atom numbering scheme is shown in Fig. 6 and packing of the molecule in the unit cell along 'a' axis is given in Fig. 7.

Fig. 2. ¹³C NMR spectrum of NVAN.

C(8) carbon atom signal is down shifted to δ 153 ppm. The C(7) carbon atom signal is shifted to down field at 141.3 ppm due to the presence of the electronegative atom N(1) and π electron delocalization on the azomethine bond. The C(9) carbon atom signal is shifted to low field (δ 139 ppm) because of the electronegative nitrogen atom N(3)³⁴. The carbon atoms nearer to -OH and -OCH₃ show

The crystallographic data along with details of structure solution refinements are given in Table 1.

Selected bond lengths and bond angles are summarized in Tables 2 and 3 respectively. NVAN crystallizes in triclinic space group P $\bar{1}$. The asymmetric unit contains two molecules of the compound. A torsion angle of 171.27(12) $^\circ$ corresponds to O(3)–C(9)–N(2)–N(1) moi-

Fig. 3. Mass spectrum of NVAN.

Fig. 4. Mode of fragmentation of NVAN.

Fig. 5. Photograph of crystalline NVAN.

Fig. 6. The molecular structure of the ligand NVAN along with atom numbering scheme.

Fig. 7. The packing of the molecule in the unit cell along the 'a' axis.

Table-1 (contd.)

Maximum and minimum transmission	0.972 and 0.965
Refinement method	Full-matrix least squares on F^2
Data/restraints/parameters	2387/3/202
Goodness-of-fit on F^2	0.922
Final R indices [$I > 2\sigma(I)$]	$R_1 = 0.0354$, $wR_2 = 0.1006$
R indices (all data)	$R_1 = 0.0421$, $wR_2 = 0.1084$
Largest difference (e \AA^{-3}) peak and hole	0.148 and -0.16
$wR_2 = [\sum w(F_o^2 - F_c^2)^2 / \sum w(F_o^2)^2]^{1/2}$ $R_1 = \sum F_o - F_c / \sum F_o $	

Table 1. Crystal data and structure refinement parameters for NVAN

Parameters	NVAN
Empirical formula	$C_{15}H_{15}N_3O_3$
Formula weight (M)	285.30
Temperature (T) (K)	296(2)
Wavelength (Mo $K\alpha$) (\AA)	0.71073
Crystal system	Triclinic
Space group	$P\bar{1}$
Lattice constants	
a (\AA)	6.9720(6)
b (\AA)	8.5733(8)
c (\AA)	11.5342(9)
α ($^\circ$)	97.965(3)
β ($^\circ$)	95.879(3)
γ ($^\circ$)	92.943(4)
Volume (V) (\AA^3)	677.69(10)
Z	2
D_{calc} (ρ) (Mg/m^3)	1.398
Absorption coefficient (μ) (mm^{-1})	0.100
$F_{(000)}$	300
Crystal size (mm^3)	$0.15 \times 0.20 \times 0.25$
Color, nature	Colorless, block
θ Range for data collection ($^\circ$)	2.78–25.0
Limiting indices	$-8 \leq h \leq 8$, $-10 \leq k \leq 10$, $-13 \leq l \leq 13$
Reflections collected	10194
Independent reflections (R_{int})	2391 (0.0218)
Observed reflections [$I > 2\sigma(I)$]	2031
Completeness to θ	25.00° (99.8%)
Absorption correction	Semi-empirical from equivalents

Table 2. Selected bond lengths (\AA) of NVAN

Bond lengths	NVAN
C(8)–N(1)	1.2726(17)
C(9)–O(3)	1.2404(15)
C(9)–N(3)	1.3520(17)
C(9)–N(2)	1.3542(17)
C(10)–N(3)	1.4119(17)
N(1)–N(2)	1.3801(15)

Table 3. Selected bond angles ($^\circ$) of NVAN

Bond angles	NVAN
N(1)–C(8)–H(8)	119.2
N(1)–C(8)–C(6)	121.66(12)
O(3)–C(9)–N(3)	124.81(12)
O(3)–C(9)–N(2)	119.64(12)
N(3)–C(9)–N(2)	115.51(11)
C(11)–C(10)–N(3)	123.15(12)
C(15)–C(10)–N(3)	117.85(12)
C(8)–N(1)–N(2)	115.47(11)
C(9)–N(2)–N(1)	121.10(11)
C(9)–N(3)–C(10)	127.05(11)

ety, which represents a trans alignment of keto carbonyl oxygen O(3) with respect to N(1). As a result, the atoms N(1) and N(3) lie *cis* to each other. This alignment favors the intramolecular hydrogen bonding interaction between N(1) and H(3)–N(3). The C(10)–N(3)–C(9)–N(2) moiety with a dihedral angle of $178.07(13)^\circ$ is almost planar. NVAN exists in the *E* conformation with respect to C(8)–N(1) bond and the atoms O(3) and N(1) also exhibit *E* conformation with respect to C(9)–N(2) bond. Hence the compound as a whole exists in the *EE* conformation in the amido form³⁹. The existence of amido form of NVAN is further confirmed by the azomethine C(8)–N(1) bond of

distance 1.2726(17) Å and the carbonyl C(9)–O(3) bond of distance 1.2404(15) Å which remain close to the formal bond distances 1.28 Å of C=N and 1.220 Å of C=O respectively^{40,41}. The N(1)–N(2) and N(2)–C(9) distances, 1.3801(15) Å and 1.3542(17) Å, respectively are intermediate between the corresponding values of single and double bonds [N–N 1.45 Å, N=N 1.25 Å and C–N 1.47 Å, C=N 1.28 Å], which gives a clear picture for an extended delocalization along the semicarbazone chain^{42,43}.

A five membered ring comprising of N(1)–N(2)–C(9)–N(3) and H(3) is formed as a result of intramolecular H-bonding interaction of N(3)–H(3)···N(1) with donor-acceptor (DA) distance of 2.634(2) Å. There exist three intermolecular H-bonding interactions between N(3)–H(3)···O(2), N(2)–H(2)···O(3) and O(2)–H(2')···O(3) with DA distances of 3.3394(15), 2.9891(15) and 2.7829(15) Å respectively. The O(2) atom can act as donor and acceptor by forming two types of H-bonding. Centrosymmetric dimers are generated by intermolecular H-bonding interactions of two neighbouring molecules as shown in Fig. 8. The H-bonding interactions are listed in Table 4. These dimers are further interconnected through π ··· π interactions of Cg(1) rings to form a two dimensional supramolecular structure which gives extra stability to the molecule. C–H··· π interactions are absent in NVAN. The π – π interactions are shown in Fig. 9.

Fig. 8. Centrosymmetric dimers formed by H-bonding interactions.

Table 4. Hydrogen bonds for NVAN [Å and °]

D–H···A	d(D–H)	d(H···A)	d(D···A)	<(DHA)
N(3)–H(3)···N(1)	0.870(9)	2.229(15)	2.6595(15)	110.4(12)
N(3)–H(3)···O(2)#1	0.870(9)	2.546(11)	3.3394(15)	152.1(13)
N(2)–H(2)···O(3)#2	0.879(9)	2.121(10)	2.9891(15)	169.3(16)
O(2)–H(2')···O(3)#3	0.845(10)	2.016(14)	2.7829(15)	151(2)

Symmetry transformations used to generate equivalent atoms :
 #1 $-x+2, -y, -z+1$ #2 $-x+1, -y, -z+2$ #3 $x, y, z-1$
 D = Donor A = Acceptor.

Fig. 9. π ··· π interactions in NVAN.

Thermal analysis :

The thermal analysis was carried out in nitrogen atmosphere from ambient upto 740 °C. The TG/DTG curves of NVAN are shown in Fig. 10. The compound is stable upto 160 °C. It undergoes decomposition in two stages. The first stage is from 160 °C to 298 °C and second from 300 °C to 740 °C. The corresponding DTG peaks are observed at 247 °C and 301 °C respectively.

Biological studies :

Antibacterial study :

The diameter of zone of inhibition formed around the wells was calculated for three different concentrations (25, 50, 100 μ L). The growth of inhibition of the standard (Gentamycin) for *Enterococcus faecalis*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *E. coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Enterobacter sp.* was found to be 23, 20, 26, 36 and 30 respectively. The diameter of zone of inhibition in mm is given in Table 5. NVAN is inactive at lower concentrations and shows moderate activity at higher concentrations compared to Gentamycin.

DNA cleavage study :

Damage of plasmid DNA means cleavage of one of the phosphodiester chains of super coiled DNA and produces relaxed open circular form and further cleavage gives linear form. Here we assessed the ability of NVAN to affect Fenton mediated strand breaks in plasmid pUC18 DNA. In a Fenton reaction, the Fe^{2+} ion formed by the reduction of Fe^{3+} by ascorbic acid, reduces hydrogen peroxide to hydroxyl radical. This reactive oxygen species are responsible for DNA cleavage⁴⁴⁻⁴⁷. The results of DNA cleavage studies have been shown in Fig. 11. The control experiment using DNA alone does not show any significant cleavage. NVAN cleaves the super coiled pUC18 DNA into linear form.

Fig. 10. TG/DTG curve of NVAN.

Fig. 11. Cleavage of pUC18 DNA by NVAN.

Lane 1 : pUC18 DNA + NVAN + Fenton's reagent, Lane 2 : pUC18 DNA alone, Lane 3 : pUC18 DNA + Fenton's reagent.

Conclusions

NVAN was synthesized and its single crystals were grown by slow evaporation technique using methanol as solvent. The single crystal X-ray diffraction revealed that NVAN crystallizes in triclinic space group $P\bar{1}$ and exists in amido form. The stoichiometry of the compound was determined using CHN analysis. The amido form of the compound was further confirmed by FT-IR, NMR and mass spectral studies. Thermal studies showed that NVAN decomposes in two stages. Antimicrobial studies revealed that the compound has moderate antibacterial activity. The DNA cleavage analysis showed that NVAN found to promote the cleavage of pUC18 DNA.

Supplementary data

CCDC 1027158 contains the supplementary crystallographic data for $C_{15}H_{15}N_3O_3$. These data can be obtained free of charge via <http://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/conts/retrieving.html>, or from the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre, 12 Union Road, Cambridge CB2 1 EZ, UK; Fax : (+44) 1223-336-033; or E-mail : deposit@ccdc.cam.ac.uk

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the SAIF, Cochin University of Science and Technology and NIIST, Thiruvananthapuram for providing the instrumental facilities. We are thankful to Biogenix Research Center, Center for Molecular Biology and Applied Science, Thiruvananthapuram for biological investigations. We are grateful to IISER, Thiruvananthapuram for providing single crystal X-ray diffraction data. One of the authors, LSR is thankful to the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research (CSIR), New Delhi for the financial assistance in the form of Senior Research Fellowship.

References

1. N. Fahmi and R. V. Singh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1996, **73**, 257.
2. J. R. Dimmock, R. N. Puthucode, J. M. Smith, M. Hetherington, J. W. Quail and U. Pugazhenth, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1996, **39**, 3984.

3. J. R. Dimmock, K. K. Sindhu, S. D. Tumber, S. K. Basran, M. Chen and J. W. Quail, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 1995, **30**, 287.
4. J. R. Dimmock, S. N. Pandeya, J. W. Quail, U. Pugazhenthii, T. M. Allen and G. Y. Kao, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 1995, **30**, 303.
5. S. N. Pandeya, P. Yogeewari and J. P. Stables, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2000, **35**, 879.
6. M. R. P. Kurup, B. Varghese, M. Sithambaresan, S. Krishnan, S. R. Sheeja and E. Suresh, *Polyhedron*, 2011, **30**, 70.
7. V. L. Siji, M. R. Sudarsanakumar and S. Suma, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 2011, **36**, 417.
8. R. N. Ram and K. Varsha, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1991, **32**, 5829.
9. T. W. Greene and P. G. Wust, "Protective Groups in Organic Synthesis", 3rd ed., John Wiley & Sons, New York, 1999.
10. B. P. Bandgar, V. S. Sadavarte, L. V. Uppalla and R. Govande, *Monatshefte für Chemie*, 2001, **132**, 403.
11. R. B. Singh, B. S. Garg and R. P. Singh, *Talanta*, 1978, **25**, 619.
12. G. Sartori, R. Ballini, F. Bigi, G. Bosica, R. Maggi and P. Righi, *Chem. Rev.*, 2004, **104**, 199.
13. F. Basuli, S. Peng and S. Bhattacharya, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2001, **40**, 1126.
14. M. Shalini, P. Yogeewari, D. Sriram and J. P. Stables, *Biomed. Pharmacother.*, 2007, **8(1)**.
15. R. Kumar, P. K. Sharma and P. M. Mishra, *Int. J. Pharm. Tech. Res.*, 2012, **4**, 266.
16. M. B. Fugu, N. P. Ndahi, B. B. Paul and A. N. Mustapha, *J. Chem. Pharm. Res.*, 2013, **5**, 22.
17. M. B. Jovanovic, S. S. Konstantinovic, S. B. Ilic, V. B. Veljkovic, *Advanced Technologies*, 2013, **2**, 38.
18. S. M. M. Ali, M. A. K. Azad, M. Jesmin, S. Ahsan, M. M. Rahman, J. A. Khanam, M. N. Islam and S. M. S. Shahriar, *Asian Pac. J. Trop. Biomed.*, 2012, **2**, 438.
19. Bruker APEX2, SAINT and XPREP, Bruker AXS, Inc., Madison, WI, 2004.
20. G. M. Sheldrick, SHELXL-97, Programs for Crystal Structure Analysis, University of Gottingen, Gottingen, Germany, 1997.
21. G. M. Sheldrick, *Acta Cryst.*, 2008, **A64**, 112.
22. K. Brandenburg, DIAMOND, Version 3.1f, Crystal Impact GbR, Bonn, Germany, 2008.
23. A. Castineiras, E. Bermejo, D. X. West, L. J. Ackerman, J. V. Martinez and S. H. Ortega, *Polyhedron*, 1999, **18**, 1463.
24. G. Madhurambal, P. Ramasamy, P. Anbusrinivasa, G. Vasudevan, S. Kavitha and S. C. Mojumdar, *J. Therm. Anal. Calorim.*, 2008, **94**, 59.
25. R. P. John, A. Sreekanth, M. R. P. Kurup, A. Usman, A. R. Ibrahim and H.-K. Fun, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 2003, **59A**, 1349.
26. P. S. Binil, M. R. Anoop, K. R. Jisha, S. Suma and M. R. Sudarsanakumar, *J. Therm. Anal. Calorim.*, 2013, **111**, 575.
27. S. Janarthanan, S. R. Sugaraj, Y. C. Rajan and S. Pandi, *J. Therm. Anal. Calorim.*, 2012, **109**, 317.
28. U. L. Kala, S. Suma, M. R. P. Kurup, S. Krishnan and R. P. John, *Polyhedron*, 2007, **26**, 1427.
29. Y.-P. Tian, W.-T. Yu, C.-Y. Zhao, M.-H. Jiang, Z.-G. Cai and H.-K. Fun, *Polyhedron*, 2002, **21**, 1217.
30. R. P. John, A. Sreekanth, M. R. P. Kurup and H.-K. Fun, *Polyhedron*, 2005, **24**, 601.
31. A. K. El-Sawaf, D. X. West, F. A. El-Saied and R. M. El-Bahnasawy, *Trans. Met. Chem.*, 1998, **23**, 649.
32. P. F. Rapheal, E. Manoj and M. R. P. Kurup, *Polyhedron*, 2007, **26**, 5088.
33. R. M. Silverstein, G. C. Bassler and T. C. Morrill, "Spectrometric Identification of Organic Compounds", 4th ed., Wiley, New York, 1981.
34. V. L. Siji, M. R. Sudarsanakumar, S. Suma and M. R. Prathapachandra Kurup, *Spectrochim. Acta, Mol. Biomol. Spectrosc.*, 2010, **76**, 22.
35. E. Hoffmann and V. Stroobant, "Mass Spectrometry : Principles and Applications", 3rd ed., Wiley, 2007.
36. B. Ze-Liang, Z. Ben-Song and X. Guan-Zhi, *Acta Chimica Sinica*, 1985, **43**, 369.
37. N. Huang, M. M. Siegel, G. H. Kruppa and F. H. Laukien, *J. Am. Soc. Mass Spectrom.*, 1999, **10**, 1166.
38. B. O. Keller, J. Sui, B. Alex, Young and R. M. Whittal, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 2008, **627**, 71.
39. V. Suni, M. R. P. Kurup and M. Nethaji, *Polyhedron*, 2007, **26**, 5203.
40. F. H. Allen, O. Kennard, D. G. Watson, I. Brammer, A. G. Orpen and R. Taylor, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans.*, 1987, **2**, S1.
41. S. R. Layana, M. Sithambaresan, V. L. Siji, M. R. Sudarsanakumar and S. Suma, *Acta Cryst.*, 2014, **E70**, o591.

42. T. A. Reena, E. B. Seena and M. R. P. Kurup, *Polyhedron*, 2008, **27**, 1825.
43. V. L. Siji, M. R. Sudarsanakumar and S. Suma, *Polyhedron*, 2010, **29**, 2035.
44. W. J. Pogożelski, T. J. McNeese and T. D. Tullius, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1995, **117**, 6428.
45. L. Jafri, F. L. Ansari, M. Jamil, S. Kalsoom, S. Qureishi and B. Mirza, *Chem. Biol. Drug. Des.*, 2012, **79**, 950.
46. G. O. Adejo and S. E. Atawodi, *Nat. Prod. Chem. Res.*, 2014, S1.
47. Y. Sindhu, C. J. Athira and M. S. Sujamol, R. S. Joseyphus and K. Mohanan, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 2013, **43**, 226.